

1 **An HCV infection module.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 We identified an HCV infection module activated in cells at 72 hours post-infection *in vitro*. The module
7 contained the genes *Chac1*, *Asns*, *Klhl24*, *Ddit4*, and *Exosc8*. The data in sum alluded to
8 exosome-associated behavior in HCV infection and addressed the role of cellular toxicity and DNA
9 damage by assigning specific gene products to these broader functions associated with pathogen infection
10 in human cells.

11 Citations

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18 GSE166428